

Technical report on the role of case studies in the restoration economy

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1 Definition of the restoration economy

The term “restoration economy” was coined by (Cunningham, 2002). The restoration economy can be defined as “the market consisting of a network of businesses, investors, consumers, and government initiatives engaging in or driving the economic activity related to ecological restoration.” (Young et al., 2023).

A criticism of this approach is the conception of the ecosystem as a commodity, which could potentially lead to competitive behavior, resulting in a piecemeal rather than a landscape approach to restoration. (Rozance et al., 2020).

2 Types of businesses. Industries in the restoration economy

Restoration is a mixture of industries (BenDor et al., 2015a). Table 1 presents the main industries in the restoration economy in the USA.

Table 1 Top industries in the restoration economy by sales in 2014, USA (BenDor et al., 2015a).

NAICS Code	Weighted Sales, 2014 (\$)	% of Total
5413-Architectural, Engineering, and Related Services	3,503,743,019	36.4
1151-Support Activities for Crop Production	2,243,711,385	23.3
2379-Other Heavy and Civil Engineering Construction	973,838,746	10.1
9241-Administration of Environmental Quality Programs	735,183,230	7.6
92-Public Administration	446,796,438	4.6
54-Professional, Scientific, and Technical Services	287,147,818	3.0
5416-Management, Scientific, and Technical Consulting Services	235,379,875	2.4
2373-Highway, Street, and Bridge Construction	213,919,343	2.2
4884-Support Activities for Road Transportation	148,640,476	1.5
1141-Fishing	126,722,762	1.3
5419-Other Professional, Scientific, and Technical Services	116,645,288	1.2
2389-Other Specialty Trade Contractors	102,139,494	1.1
531-Real Estate	50,447,677	0.5
23-Construction	48,741,430	0.5
1153-Support Activities for Forestry	21,560,834	0.2
Other Industries	229,483,090	3.9

Business functions within the restoration economy include (BenDor et al., 2015b):

- Real estate/Site acquisition

- Planning, design, and engineering
- Physical restoration (earth moving, planting, burning)
- Monitoring
- Landscaping supplies
- Other supplies
- Legal services
- Financing
- Consulting
- Other

The restoration economy includes environmental conservation, restoration, and mitigation actions (BenDor et al., 2015a).

3 Restoration projects

3.1 Types of restoration projects

The goals of restoration projects can be (Nellemann and Corcoran, 2010):

- Biodiversity conservation
- Water supply
- Health and wastewater management
- Food security
- Climate change mitigation
- Disaster prevention and mitigation

The types of restoration works have been classified (BenDor et al., 2015b) as:

- Terrestrial habitat restoration and management
- Wetland restoration and management
- Aquatic and riparian restoration and management
- Marine and estuarine restoration and management
- Mitigation banking
- Enhanced stewardship (timber, ranch, farm)
- Invasive species control and management
- Clean-ups and contamination management
- Species conservation and management
- Other

A decision-tree-based classification of restoration (sub-)projects is presented in figure 1 and table 2 (Gerwing et al., 2023):

- Reclamation
- Rehabilitation
- Rewilding
- Landscape restoration
- Intra-ecosystem restoration
- Ecological reclamation
- Reference condition restoration

The restoration can be classified by ecosystem (BenDor et al., 2015a) as:

- Forest
- Watershed
- Invasive species removal

- Grassland
- Upland
- Wetland
- Tidal marsh
- Fish passage
- River
- In-stream
- Hydrologic reconnection
- Riparian
- Reef

From a geographic scale perspective, the restoration can be classified as (BenDor et al., 2015a):

- County
- State
- National

Figure 1 Decision tree for restoration type based on project goals (scope) (Gerwing et al., 2023)

Table 2 Proposed restoration definitions (Gerwing et al., 2023)

Term	Proposed definition
Reclamation	The process of making severely degraded habitat fit for cultivation or a state suitable for some human use
Rehabilitation	Management actions that aim to reinstate a level of ecosystem functioning on degraded sites, where the goal is renewed and ongoing provision of ecosystem services rather than the biodiversity and integrity of a designated native reference ecosystem
Ecological Restoration	The process of assisting the recovery of an ecosystem that has been degraded, damaged, or destroyed to benefit native biodiversity
Rewilding	The process of rebuilding, often following major human disturbance, a natural ecosystem(s) by restoring natural processes and the complete or near complete foodweb at all trophic levels as a self-sustaining and resilient ecosystem using biota that would have been present had the disturbance not occurred
Landscape Restoration	Activities that seek to recover landscape-level ecological integrity by focusing on the restoration of landscape structure, dynamics, and function, with a particular focus on restoring critical interactions between ecosystems or landscape units
Intra-Ecosystem Restoration	Activities that target a limited subset of ecosystem components, with efforts constrained within a single ecosystem and landscape unit
Ecological Reclamation	Activities that aim to assist the recovery of an ecosystem, species, or community to states outside those predicted by native reference models, or divergent from the variety of conditions observed in native and (or) nearby reference habitats
Reference Condition Restoration	Activities that aim to assist the recovery of an ecosystem, species, or community to states within those predicted by native reference models or within the variation of conditions observed in native and (or) nearby reference habitats

3.2 Legislative, social, and political environment of restoration projects

The drivers of the restoration industry are (BenDor et al., 2015a) :

- Public
 - Regulatory drivers
 - Programs for public procurement of restoration
 - Complex regional initiatives
 - Internal agency policies
- Private investments
 - For sustainability and social responsibility goals
 - Philanthropic

Types of markets highly relevant for ecological restoration (Nielsen-Pincus and Moseley, 2012) are:

- Grant market
- Contracting market
- Labor market

The stakeholders in restoration case studies have been classified as (Brancalion et al., 2022):

- Watershed committee
- Farmer
- Government
 - Municipal
 - State
 - Federal
- Individual micro entrepreneur
- Private companies
 - Micro
 - Small
 - Medium
 - Large
- NGOs
 - Local/municipal
 - Regional/state

- National
- International
- Cooperatives, associations, and seed networks

Social anti-restoration mechanisms potentially functioning as stressors are (Helm et al., 2023):

- Inertia
- Elite defense of status quo, growth logics, “business as usual”
- Erosion of the social contract
- Managerialism & marketization
- Decoupling, greenwashing
- Alienation, precarity, increased workload, instrumentalism
- Comfort/safety of tradition, strengthened cultural worldview/ self-esteem
- Suppression, denial, ridicule

Pro-restoration mechanisms are (Helm et al., 2023):

- Stakeholder pressure (regulatory, students, staff, publics)
- Espoused values (climate concern/ consciousness/literacy)

3.3 Internal variables of restoration projects

A taxonomy of funding mechanisms (Dunn-Capper et al., 2023) Includes:

- Domestic budget allocation and donations (Governmental budget allocation, philanthropy, and donations from conservation NGOs)
- Subsidies
- Biodiversity offsets
- Payments for ecosystem services
- Certification
- Direct biodiversity fees
- Blended finance models, which combine public and private funding

Cost components can be classified as (Brancalion et al., 2022):

- Labor
- Machinery
- Inputs

The number of jobs created by the project is also an essential internal variable (Brancalion et al., 2022).

3.4 Functioning of restoration projects

The functioning of restoration projects depends on the complexity of the relationship between organizations, and restoration projects are classified as (Galatowitsch, 2022):

- Restoration-focused organization pursues a project
- A group within a large organization pursues a project
- Several restoration organizations form a partnership to pursue a large or complex project
- Multiple restoration organizations receive funds secured by a intermediary to arrange local stakeholders & pursue projects
- Several restoration organizations, including a large one, form a partnership to pursue a large or complex project

- Several groups within several large organizations pursue large or complex projects
- Several groups within a large organization pursue large or complex projects

The restoration methods can be classified as (Krishnan and Osuri, 2022):

- Passive
- Active
- With intervention continuum

Another classification of restoration methods is (Brancalion et al., 2019):

- Natural regeneration
- Assisted regeneration
- Direct seeding
- Seedling planting
- Enrichment planting

Implementation activities can be classified as (Brancalion et al., 2022):

- Protection against disturbances
- Weed control
- Soil preparation
- Planting/seedling
- Irrigation
- Replanting
- Others

Types of restoration costs by activities are (Kimball et al., 2015):

- Site preparation
- Seeding and planting
- Maintenance

Another classification of major expenditure categories in restoration grants includes (Nielsen-Pincus and Moseley, 2012) :

- Construction and equipment contractors
- Wholesale and retail trade
- Non-profit organizations
- Logging and forestry operations
- Local government
- Technical service providers
- Others
- Initial leakage (vendors located outside of the local economy)

The duration of maintenance can be classified as (Brancalion et al., 2022):

- 1 to 3 months
- 3 to 6 months
- 6 to 12 months
- 12 to 24 months
- 24 to 30 months
- 30 to 60 months

4 Resilience of restoration projects and organizations

External and internal stressors can disturb the functioning of restoration projects and organizations. However, mechanisms such as resistance, elasticity, adaptability, and transformability can make restoration projects and businesses resilient to single or multiple stressors.

Types of stressors of restoration outcomes or longevity (Galatowitsch, 2022) Include:

- unstable funding
- leadership change,
- new or unmitigated stresses to the ecosystem
- Unanticipated responses to restoration actions
- gaps in knowledge and expertise
- variable levels of commitment of participants

Critical capacities and functions for the resilience of restoration projects are (Galatowitsch, 2022):

- Situation Awareness
 - Staff engagement
 - Learning and knowledge
 - Adaptive decision making
 - Collective sensemaking
- Governance and Leadership
 - Leadership
 - Unity of purpose
 - Self-organization
 - Decision making
- Internal Resources
 - Technical capacity
 - Prevention of silos
 - Innovation and creativity
 - Administrative competence
- External Relations
 - Partnerships and collaborations
 - Capacity gap-filling
 - Professional and policy influence
- Change Readiness
 - Strategic direction
 - Adaptability
 - Transformability

Indicators of restoration projects' and restoration businesses' resilience are (Galatowitsch, 2022):

- Access to essential resources
- Acquisition of essential human and financial resources
- Administrative direction
- Buffering (organizational-level contingency planning)
- Capacity for organizational transformation
- Catalyst for network formation and collaboration
- Change management
- Clarity of roles and responsibilities
- Communications during disruptions
- Contracting capacity
- Detection of trends and emerging challenges
- Development of best practices
- Devolved decision-making

- Diversified network
- Early warning signal reporting
- Established relationships for back-up capacity
- Goal-setting for projects
- Individual experts' influence beyond the organization
- Informed decision-making
- Internal communications
- Knowledge acquisition
- Knowledge leveraging
- Knowledge sharing
- Leadership for learning, collective sense-making, conflict management
- Leadership succession planning
- Level of shared responsibility
- Management across different cultures and norms
- Management of human and financial resources
- Mechanisms to avoid silos
- Organizational awareness of political and power environment
- Organizational goal-setting
- Organizational strategic planning
- Portfolio-scale goal-setting
- Pro-active posture
- Project contingency planning
- Project goal-setting and monitoring
- Project record-keeping
- Promotion of innovation, creativity, and excellence
- Recognition of the organization's work
- Risk management (resources)
- Simulation of disruptions
- Strategic vision and outcome expectancy
- Training to develop internal expertise
- Translation of vision to actionable plans
- Understanding of risks and consequences of failures

4.1 The resilience of large-scale ecosystem restoration projects

A book with 5 case studies coined the LER notion in the business of ecological restoration (Doyle and Drew, 2012) The key property for LER to be LER is the large complexity of the system related to the natural, legislative, institutional, funding, project structure, organizational network to implement the project, and the economic sectors involved in implementing the project. Success and failure depend on the complex interplay between the variables listed in chapters 3.2, 3.3, and 3.4. and the right way is somewhat unique to each case.

In this context, the uptake of explicit scientific information is as essential as the tacit strategic knowledge of practitioners, stakeholders, and policymakers (Hulme, 2014). From the perspective of scientific models, including the relevant tacit knowledge, means adding the business perspective of „people who do on-the-ground implementation” in the socio-ecological theory (Mohr and Metcalf, 2017): „Balancing ecological and business objectives, managing risk, learning from failure, being open to innovations, engaging in monitoring to gauge project success on multiple dimensions and to improve restoration practice, and understanding the perspective of on-the-ground personnel all present business challenges.”

4.2 The role of case studies in increasing the resilience

The role of case studies is to provide hints about what worked and did not work in other situations related to one kind of variable or another, and on this basis to prepare adaptive management and increase the resilience of each new project.

A standard narrative of a case study (Nellemann and Corcoran, 2010) This includes sections dealing with the drivers and pressures causing the deterioration, changes in the state of the system and their impact on species, habitats, natural resources, and ecosystem services, the political, logistical, ecological, and social context of restoration, the description of the restoration approach and its implementation, the successes and failures of the restoration effort, and where the interested reader can find more details.

One can notice that the objective of having resilient LER projects surpasses the criticism of restoration economics, as based on a conception of the ecosystem as a commodity (Rozance et al., 2020) by the importance given to capacities such as situation awareness and external relations (Galatowitsch, 2022). Case studies for the LER business may also help surpass ideological tensions related to restoration approaches by focusing on pragmatic restoration success.

The case studies might also stimulate the integration of ecosystem markets and the blending of public and private finance for better management of the trade-offs between different restoration objectives and ecosystem services (Reed et al., 2022). The professional associations in restoration ecology can work as a trusted intermediary, broker, and platform to build trust and lower the transaction costs of future restoration projects (Reed et al., 2022). They may also stimulate the diversification of other businesses through restoration to build resilience into their business model (Hill, 2019) and in this way to further increase the size of the restoration economy.

5 Conclusions

The key property for LER to be LER is the **large complexity** of the system related to the natural, legislative, institutional, and funding variables, project structure, organizational network to implement the project, and the economic sectors involved in implementing the projects.

The link between case studies and resilience is that tacit knowledge/know-how is essential when dealing with large complexity. **There is no strictly scientific solution for resilient LER projects and resilient LER businesses.**

Scientific knowledge can be transferred by structures (models) and data (variables and measurements/estimations of their values), and **tacit knowledge/know-how** can be transferred to some extent by narratives (stories, opinions, examples in everyday language).

We organize the template for case studies to provide structure (scientific approach) and facilitate the delivery of tacit knowledge through the narrative.

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Annex 1: Draft of the case study template

- Checkboxes for a structural perspective on the case study and search in a repository
- Structure of the narrative

Checkboxes (the table will be filled with a selection of items from the technical report)

Type of restoration		
By goal • A • B • ...	By ecosystem	By geographic scale
The environment of the project		
Regulating drivers • A • B ...	Types of market	Stakeholder
Anti-restoration mechanism • A • B ...	Pro-restoration mechanism	
Structure of the project		
Funding mechanisms • A • B ...	Cost components	Number of jobs
Governance and leadership • A • B ...	Technical capacity	
Functioning of the project		
Relationships between organisations and project • A • B ...	Restoration methods	Implementation activities
Expenditure categories • A • B ...	Duration of maintenance	
Resilience of the project		
Types of stressors • A • B ...	Existing critical capacities and functions	Indicators of resilience

Structure of the narrative

1 Introduction

- Drivers and pressures causing the deterioration
- Changes in the state of the system
- The impact on species, habitats, natural resources, and ecosystem services
- The political, logistical, ecological, and social context of restoration
- The description of the restoration approach and its implementation
- The successes and failures of the restoration effort

2 Life stories, experiences, and personal opinions of the people involved in the project

3 Where the interested reader can find more details